

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING INFORMATICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6576699>

At present, the educational process requires constant improvement, as priorities and social values are changing: scientific and technological progress is increasingly recognized as a means achieving a level of production that best meets the ever-increasing needs of a person, the development of the spiritual wealth of the individual. Therefore, the current situation in the preparation of school graduates requires a radical change in the strategy and tactics of education. Multimedia is the representation of objects and processes not by a traditional textual description, but with the help of photos, videos, graphics, animation, sound, that is, in all forms known today. Here we have two main advantages - qualitative and quantitative. Qualitatively new possibilities are obvious if we compare verbal descriptions with direct audiovisual presentation. Quantitative advantages are expressed in the fact that the multimedia environment is much higher in terms of information density. Indeed, one page of text, as you know, contains about 2 KB of information. The teacher pronounces this text for about 1-2 minutes. For the same minute, a full-screen video brings about 1.2 GB of information. That is why "it is better to see once than hear a million times." The methodology for using multimedia technologies involves: - improvement of the learning management system at various stages of the lesson; - strengthening the motivation for learning; - improving the quality of education and upbringing, which will increase the information culture of students; - increasing the level of training of students in the field of modern information technologies; - a demonstration of the capabilities of the computer, not only as a means for the game. Multimedia lessons help to solve the following didactic tasks: acquire basic knowledge of the subject; systematize acquired knowledge; develop self-control skills; to form motivation for teaching in general and for computer science in particular; provide educational and methodological assistance to OH students in independent work on educational material. This technology can be considered as an explanatory and illustrative teaching method, the main purpose of which is to organize the assimilation of information by students by communicating educational material and ensuring its successful perception, which is enhanced when visual memory is connected. When multimedia technologies are used in a lesson, the structure of the lesson does not fundamentally change. It still retains all the main stages, perhaps only

their temporal characteristics will change... The study of computer science using interactive methods allows you to activate the cognitive activity of students, develop the ability to learn independently, develop teamwork skills, develop and form communication skills, and most importantly increase learning motivation. Interactive method (Scheme 3). Interactive ("Inter" is mutual, "act" is to act) - means to interact, is in the mode of conversation, dialogue with someone. In other words, unlike active methods, interactive ones are focused on a wider interaction of students not only with the teacher, but also with each other and on the dominance of student activity in the learning process. Chapter 2 In the period of rapid informatization of our society, there is a growing need for the education and upbringing of children who are able to live in an open society, able to communicate and interact with all the diversity of the real world, having a holistic view of the world and its informational unity. Therefore, interactive learning becomes important for the development of children. Interactive learning is, first of all, interactive learning, during which the interaction between the teacher and the student takes place.[3,c There are a huge number of interactive learning technologies (work in pairs; rotational (replaceable) triples; carousel; work in small groups; aquarium; unfinished sentence; brainstorming; Brownian motion; decision tree; court on one's own behalf; civil hearings; role-playing (business) game; press method; take a position; discussion, debate). Let's consider the use of some interactive technologies in computer science lessons in more detail. Students really like this kind of work like the "Carousel", when two rings are formed: inner and outer. The inner ring is the students sitting motionless, and the inner one is the students who change every 30 seconds. Thus, they manage to speak several topics in a few minutes and try to convince the interlocutor of their rightness. When working with students in grades 6-8, it is more appropriate to start with the simplest forms of group work ("pinwheel", "big circle", "aquarium"). The value in these forms is that they allow the child not only to express his opinion, view and assessment, but also, having heard the arguments of his partner in the game, sometimes abandon his point of view or significantly change it. The simplest form of group interaction is the "big circle ". The work takes place in three stages. The first stage. The group sits on chairs in a large circle. The teacher formulates the problem. The second stage. Within a certain time (approximately 10 minutes), each student individually, on his/her sheet, writes down the proposed measures to solve the problem. Third stage. In a circle, each student reads out his proposals, the group silently listens (does not criticize) and votes on each item - whether to include it in the general decision, which is recorded on the board as the conversation progresses.

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